

OF HEREDITY IN THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY AND SICK ORGANISM.

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Abstract: this in the article healthy and the patient your organism differences , health of the concept content essence , man in formation heredity and hereditary of characters importance illuminated .

Key word: health , environment , society , heredity , organism , development , psyche, dissimulation .

Health what?

All Union health society by in 1948 acceptance made : " Health is this only disease and physical from defects case to be not but _ complete physical , mental and social development . " " Individual health of a person is an organism pathological without shifts , environment in optimal connection with , all functions to each other adapted natural status ." (GZDemchinkova , NLPolonsky); " Health is this of the organism surroundings to the environment adjectival and optimal life activities as well full bloody work activities providing giver systemic-functional of properties mutually harmonized is the sum "; " The individual health of a person is in the body all substance exchange of processes harmonized unit in the body all system and small optimal life of systems activity for conditions creates " (ADAdo); " Health is this of a person active of life maximum in duration biological , physiological , psychological of functions , to labor ability and social activity save to stay and improvement process "(VPKaznacheev).

Scientists according to " Health is a person vital of activity spiritual , emotional , psychic , physical of the fields simple status being , this condition a person personality , ability and of ability prosperity , environment with continuously depending on it for responsibility understanding for comfortable conditions creates ". Valeology in " individual (human) health " and " population "health " is different . Individual health is this to the environment of adaptation dynamic process being scientists _ according to the individuum to health his external environment , living condition and of others different character to the effect adaptability , durability and reaction as to look need _ According to V. I. Dubrovsky (1999) , health evaluation criteria as follows :– given stage physical to work ability and morphological development level _ special the work ability restrictive chronic diseases , physical of defects availability ;– social comforts , get married variable to the conditions flexibility of the environment

uncomfortable of factors to the effect endurance of the organism external to the environment to the effect reaction save _ Health level how defined ? Population of health status or society health level evaluation for different character from indicators used : demographic (birth , death , average age), morbidity , morbidity , disability and b. indicators . Health to what depends ? Heredity - 20% Environment environment - 20% Medical help level - 10% Marriage style - 50% Current at the time health evaluation for basis to be characters the following to groups is separated :

1. Physical harmonic development level _
2. Basic functional systems and whole of the organism reserve opportunities ;
3. The body immunity protection and nonspecific resistance level _
4. Chronic and born diseases , development defects presence or absence ;
5. Man health spiritual and social amenities reflection bringer personal characteristics level _

Individual health indicators :

Genetic - genotype , dysembryogenesis , hereditary of defects absence ;

Biochemical - biological tissues and liquids indicators ;

Metabolic - calm in case and from downloads after substance exchange level _

Morphological - physical development level , type of constitution (morphotype)

Functional-organs and of systems functional state : - peace the norm is reaction standard - reserve capabilities , functional type.

Psychological - feeling , thinking , intellectual fields : - half balls dominance - high nerve type of activity - temperament - superiority doer instinct type.

Social - spiritual purposeful directions public values , high goals , claims level and requirements reamulation and etc

Clinical disease _ of signs lack of Health level material to security depends _

Material security level marriage style significant effect to show no doubt Disease most of the time to health opposite condition as viewed : Worldwide health

society dictionary according to the disease is " normal ". any of the cases subjective and objective is a deviation ". Illness come exit reasons the following :

- of the organism (functional system , organ or of tissue) less mobility , this own in turn normative low reaction to stimulation doer to lack of training take comes ;

- harmonized of management violation , and poisonous substances accumulated to stay take will come and etc. _ - poisoning , radiation as a result of cells damage ;

- external of the environment change , skin , muscles , internal of organs of cells functions structure take comes ; - of the psyche disorder ,

nervousness factor (stess) influence as a result appear will be Each _ disease

the following periods according to develops : - latent or hidden period ; - disease the first symptoms (prodromal) period ; - disease the climax received period ; - the disease completion , recovery period ; Getting sick during different in the body changes face to give can _ First of all assimilation processes - different of substances organism by appropriation and their tissues for necessary has been to compounds rotation _ Dissimilation is _ alive of matter decay is a process (complex of compounds decomposition of energy- rich compounds energy separation). Dystrophy , atrophy , cold , blood rotation violation and b. pathology types is considered Dystrophy - tissue (cell) metabolism violation proteins , fats , carbohydrates , minerals in tissues (cells) _ or salts from exchange come out , general or partial , congenital or after appear has been system changes with observed . Atrophy - organs and tissues of functions decline and of size decrease . Hypertrophy - cells the number or of size increase as a result of the organ enlargement . Health and disease between case " third is called " state " . Immunity (Latin immunitas - one from the thing free to be) – of the organism genetic a stranger information carrier substance or of creatures protection . Heredity and health _ Your child development pregnant from being , gender and biological fund from detection begins , but in the child's organism there is has been genetic hereditary characters sure social in the environment done is increased .

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